

Digital twin for existing buildings

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Abstract

Digital twins are a powerful tool first used by NASA to demonstrate how real objects can interact with virtual objects. However, the precise application and interpretation of digital twins (DT) in various areas is still under development. Modern technologies are influencing the way buildings are maintained and managed. The idea of digital twins (DT), which act as virtual duplicates of actual assets, processes and systems, is at the heart of this revolution. However, difficulties in the development and assimilation of these twins continue to hinder their wider acceptance. Alternative approaches are necessary because, despite potential benefits, the construction industry lacks standardised methods for integrating digital twins. In addition, digital twins are integrated into the workflow implementation at various project phases, starting from the design phase to the post-construction phase. Challenges, particularly significant time and cost constraints, emerge when developing digital twins for existing buildings that lack 3D models. Therefore companies are prioritising projects that integrate digital twins into the whole lifecycle.

Regardless of the level of complexity, digital twins offer many advantages. Nevertheless, the absence of readily available as-built building information modeling models presents a substantial obstacle to commencing Digital Twin development. This thesis addresses this obstacle by proposing a framework that utilises alternative digital techniques, methods and scenarios.

This study provides a theoretical foundation and then evaluates the latest technologies and workflows in creating digital twins by comparing solutions to identify key components and attributes essential for their efficient development. By carefully examining the digital twin concept and its benefits, this research aims to facilitate the practical implementation of digital twins in the AECO Industry. The thesis also outlines a detailed framework for digital twins in situations where an as-built BIM model is not available, addressing challenges and key issues while analysing existing workflows and methodologies. The aim of this study is to provide useful insights and recommendations for organisations that want to develop digital twins for the maintenance and operation of existing buildings without an as-built BIM model. This is done through the use of a comprehensive analysis and demonstration framework with an implementation on a industry practice.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/500AnEx-08A>

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